

The Nature of Sex

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 15, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Body, Behavior, Human, Sex, Sexual Behavior, Orgasm, Commodity</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5203276</p>	<p><i>The human is the need of the body and the body is the ability to satisfy the object. The unity between the body and the person is the body's need and the ability to satisfy the object. Man is the means, the body is purpose, and vice versa. Lifetime is filled by a succession of means and purpose that make the need secure. One of the basic needs is sex. The sexual act is the best act in the relationship between bodies and people. The good thing is to take the happiness of others as your own; perceive the unhappiness of others as one's own powerlessness. Sexual behavior is an individual, creative and responsible behavior in relation to the object. If the object of sex is not perceived, sexual orientation such as heterosexual, homosexual, bisexual, and asexuality does not appear. Sex and money are still popular needs, while sexual acts, people, and bodies are commodities. When sexual behavior is a commodity, tools, means, aphrodisiac, and people are produced. Sex plays the role of distributing products, overcoming social divisions, eliminating discrimination, and maintaining the race is a natural development process.</i></p>

Introduction

Sex is one of the essential needs of life, but until now, sex and sexual behavior are understood very differently. Each ethnic group has different cultural traditions, the concept of virginity, sexual standards, sexual behavior, love, marriage, and family are different. Especially in today's conditions, sexual needs, sexual behaviors, and sexual orientations are very diverse in heterosexual, homosexual, bisexual, asexual; phenomena of in vitro reproduction, surrogacy, sperm banking, surgical engineering of the genitals, trafficking in children, women, and sex slaves appeared. Aphrodisiacs, tools, and means of supporting sexual satisfaction are produced and sold very popularly. Contagious diseases, social problems arise due to sexual behavior. Sexual behavior is a commodity, it is exchanged, bought and sold in different forms to earn money and power. Without seeing the role of sex in life, it is difficult to solve social welfare problems. This article contributes to a multi-dimensional view of sex from dialectical and historical materialism methodology.

Literature Review

The article titled *The Nature of Sex* is new research compared to previous works but it is inherited from different studies. According to *Human Sciences* (2020), real people serve as a premise for scientific research. Real human needs are the object of perception. *Money with perfecting human* (2020) clarifies that money is an equivalent object for exchange, then human is a commodity. People and standards are unified, so standards are commodities. Humans are an equivalent object for exchange, money and standards are commodities. People are valuable when it is the need of all. *Discussion about the private - owned and private individual* (2020) distinguishes between private - owned and private individual. Private - owned is the ownership of products by labor. Private individual is the ownership of the product not by labor. Private individual is the cause of bad habit and laziness, it is the cause of the antagonistic division of labor. *Humans' value and cost* (2020) makes it clear that people are value. Thereby clarifying the feeling, subjective feeling, human – made sense and practical feeling in performing the behavior. Connecting people by behavior and standards is like exchanging, buying and selling different goods to earn a living. Love is exchanged for wealth, money makes false love appear. According to *The Nature of Education* (2020), humans liberate themselves from the natural world by work, the norms make people slaves. The norm of sexual behavior makes people fake and each other's means of subsistence. *The Nature of Power* (2020) presents power as the power used in creating and educating each other in human nature. Thereby making it clear that possession of property, property is the owner of that property. If you want to own wealth, you must love its owner. *The consistency between the truth and deception during humans' development process* (2021) clarifies direct relationships that are necessarily perceived as truths. Truth is popular demand. Necessities that are not fully realized give rise to falsehoods. Lies are hidden by standards. *The Nature of State* (2021) presents the human being in relation to its products. The state appears to be the fair needs of citizens, but the state becomes the means of living for officials. When taking standards, laws, and money as equals in exchange, buying and selling, the inequality between people deepens. *The Spiritual Goods* (2021) clarifies the difference between people and real people. Man is the need of the body and the body is the

ability to satisfy human needs. Human needs are very rich and diverse, but after all, real people have the need to be human. Individuals are an individual, scarce of nature, but individuals are exchanged, bought and sold as spiritual goods. *The nature of human life* (2021) has shown that nature, human, and body are a unity. The body is a defective product. Perfection of the body requires a human role. Humans make equal objects to exchange, buy and sell, all are commodities. Commodities are produced to connect defective parts of the body, connecting all things in the universe, but human is always the center. When people are commodities, people are discriminated against. The existence of the family is a common spiritual need, but it has become a tool for patriarchal livelihood, deepening injustice. *Exclusive Spiritual Goods* (2021) clarifies the body in relation to people, behavior, norms, individuality, creation, labor, exclusive behavior, exclusive individuality, freedom, labor, possessions, money. Distinguish between physical behavior, human behavior, personal behavior to clarify responsible behavior and irresponsible behavior, but sexual behavior has not been studied. The above documents do not clarify the sexual nature but it is the database to clarify *The Nature of Sex*.

Research Method

Method and Data

The research is based on the worldview and the methodology of Marxist philosophy, and at the same time uses specific research methods such as analysis and synthesis, logic and history, inductive and interpretation, abstraction, generalization, comparison, comparison and literary methods for research and presentation.

Results and Discussion

The body and the person satisfy the needs by behavior

The object is the means of the body and the body is the ability to satisfy the object, so when taking the reality of life as the goal, man is the need of the body. The human and the body are a unity, that unity is both the ability to satisfy the object and the need of the body. Theoretically, it is possible to separate the person from the body to perceive. The body's ability to satisfy is the object of knowledge of the natural sciences, while the needs of the body are the object of human science. Natural science and human science have a unity in the study of behavior. By behavior the body makes man alive, or man makes the body come alive. If the body doesn't exist then everything is meaningless and the body is eternal everything is superfluous. Everything becomes superfluous to the body, then man becomes meaningless. All objects that are meaningful to the body are values, so man is the value of the body. Man is the value of the body, man is the need of the body. Man protects his own body with all that he can, no matter what the body, form, circumstances. Man is the means, and the body is the purpose. When man is the purpose, the body is the means. Life is a succession, interchanging means and purpose. Man becomes the counterpart to all when the body reveals itself through its object.

The objects that correspond to the needs of the body, the person is one of the objects that are directly perceived. Without the senses, man is not awakened, human existence is absent, and human perception is superfluous. Humans are created by objects through constantly developing senses, subjective sensations are awakened, individuality appears. Behavior changes the state of feeling so creativity is formed accordingly. The impact of the object directly on the body causes sensations to appear so the individual understands the body's need for its objects. The sensations are equally valuable in helping the body to be maintained but at the same time it creates the tendency of perfection by creating needs or transforming the object of response accordingly. Each body has different circumstances and conditions, so the creation of different senses is a subjective feeling. Man discovers himself by sensations and behaviour. The body's inability to react to objects is due to either the absence of sensations, or the feeling worn out. Eliminate sensory wear by changing conditions, or practice life, or create new needs, senses are perfected, human – made sense are awakened. Then subjective feeling appears in relation to its object. An object has meaning when it exists in relation to the individual who has a need for that object.

The relationship between the body and the object takes man as the purpose, then the body and the object are the means; but when taking the body, the object as the purpose, the means are created by human behavior. The object of existence for the body is need; the need for human existence is the capacity to live. The need has an increase in quantity, the subjective feeling that corresponds to it is right to that level. The richness of the object, but the new senses have not yet appeared or the senses have not been completed, or the human – made sense have not been awakened, the illusion and imagination appear. Sensory defects, or malformed senses, opposite sensations appear. Even when new objects appear but there are no human – made sense or senses, opposite sensations arise. Unable to distinguish colors and sounds for the blind and deaf, the imagined world of colors and sounds becomes the object of subjective sensations of people with sensory impairments. People with disabilities become a common phenomenon, people without disabilities will become isolated and opposite. Objects bring individuality, the opposite makes individuals different in subjective feeling, while objects are common, making people similar in practical feeling.

Real man is the object of life. All life has human attributes, so protecting life is the function and task of real people. The object of man is not death, the afterlife, but the object of man is living reality. Life brings people back to living reality, making people fully reveal their nature in maintaining life and race. The needs of the body are expressed through specific objects, the real life shows satisfaction in the behaviors. The strength of the body

corresponds to its object, the power of man to face life and maintain the race. The life and maintenance of the race have a direct relationship between the body is inevitable. This direct relationship satisfies different needs, but ultimately sustains life and breeds by different behaviors. Human behavior differs from animal activity in that it creates needs.

Lifetime is filled with successive means and purposes that make life secure. The body can satisfy many needs at once, but humans cannot. People do not satisfy many needs at the same time because it is not possible to perform many behaviors at the same time, if the behavior has not become unconscious, instinctive or the perfection of behavior. When people satisfy one need, they must give in to the other. Having no need and having a need are essentially the same, but different in the object to be met, people who satisfy the need for one object do not satisfy the need for the other object at the same time. Even giving up a need so that there is no longer a need is the act of fulfilling another need. Satisfying needs in general and sexual needs in particular depends not only on different behaviors but also on the object of demand. A need is a necessary condition, then its satisfaction is a sufficient condition. One of the basic needs of human development is the performance of individual behavior. Sexual needs are satisfied by individual behavior.

Satisfying sexual needs by personal behavior

Nature is man's need, man's life corresponds to nature. Humans are the needs of nature, so natural relations maintain human existence. Maintaining human existence is maintaining life and lineage. Nature maintains life by giving and reciprocating to people to satisfy different needs, including sexual needs. Humans are not rewarded with natural orgasms, the maintenance of the species does not occur. Natural relations produce human beings with all orgasms. "The relationship of man to woman is the most natural relationship between man and man. Therefore, in that relationship, the natural behavior of humans has become human behavior" (Marx& Engel, p.166). The life of the body is the purpose, and the satisfaction of sexual orgasm is the consequences. But when sexual orgasm is the purpose, reproduction is the consequence. Sex is one of the essential needs of life, sexual behavior is like eating, drinking, sleeping, resting. If you don't eat one, eat another; If you don't drink this glass of water, drink the other glass; If you don't sleep now, rest another time. Sexual acts need to be done but there is creativity, so if you don't do it at this time, you can do it at another time, if you are not satisfied with this object, you will be satisfied with the other object, if not, you can otherwise, it is not for the sake of this moment or for the other. All forms, objects, times and places of performing sexual acts are selected and creative.

The body and the person are united in maintaining life, the sexual behavior between heterosexuals is united in maintaining the species. In a unity, the body is defective, the human being is perfect, but there is mutual compensation in maintaining life. "The body is the defects of nature placed in man, and the wealth is the perfection of man placed in nature by the body" (Quoc, 2021d, p. 342). When men are perfect, women are defective and vice versa, but there is mutual compensation in maintaining the race. The mutual compensation between the body and people in maintaining life, but the mutual compensation between people and the bodies in the balance of life, maintaining the species. This balance manifests itself in sexual gratification. The sexual need to connect, exchange and create directly between bodies and people in a realistic way.

Humans and bodies are a unity in behavior, the exchange and connection between acts is the exchange and connection between bodies and people. The relationship of exchange and connection is a direct creation between the acts of sex, which consequentially maintain the species. People face directly with the body honestly in sexual acts, it also fully manifests in sexual relations. Sexual relations reveal human nature directly through the body in behavior. The sexual act is the truest act in the relationship between bodies and people. The good thing is to see the happiness of others as your own happiness; Seeing the unhappiness of others as one's own impotence. People compensate each other by satisfying sexual needs is the most realistic. People can only give each other what one has that the other needs to use for what each other wants. Grief, anxiety, stress, thinking, blood concentrates on the brain, while sexual behavior occurs, blood concentrates in two places, making the body imbalance.

Human sexual satisfaction is a sexual act. The sexual act is one of the bodily acts. If the physical act is to maintain the natural life, then the sexual act is to maintain the balance of the body. The baby can get an erection by unconscious, instinctive; The genital organ may be directly admired but it does not yet have the need to perform the sexual act. Objects of body satisfaction are inevitable, common survival in the unconscious, instinctive. "The formation of a fetus in the body is unconscious, instinctive, but raising children is a physical act. Unconscious, instinct is inside, and behavior is outside but unified in the body. When the object of the body's need becomes scarce, the behavior of choosing the object of the need arises. This change is by behavior to satisfy the needs of the body" (Quoc, 2021e, p.2571). Eating, drinking, breathing, seeing, hearing, walking, resting, sleeping... are the needs of the body required in external objects to ensure the forms of energy for survival.

Hunger and thirst are the needs for food and drink, manifested in the lack of energy of the body, sleep, rest, and sex are the needs of the body to be balanced. The need for sleep, rest, and sex is fulfilled by physical acts, but the object of satisfaction is different. Lifetime is performing successive acts to ensure body balance. When there is a phase difference, an imbalance, there are different behaviors to adjust the body to suit life. Behavioral

diversification is inevitable in the maturation process of the body. The phase difference, loss of sexual orientation often occurs during the development of the sexual organs and at puberty. Androgen production makes the sex organs form and complete. Androgen causes desire, excitement makes the formation of sexual needs appear. But androgen imbalance is the cause of genital deformity.

Different forms of energy help the body to grow, mature and at the same time store energy. "External objects compensate for the internal needs of the body, although different forms of existence, but conserve energy. Physical satisfaction through different forms of energy causes different behavior. Inner lack of energy manifests itself in the needs of external objects" (Quoc,2021e, p.2571). The formation of fetuses, sperms, eggs, hormones, antibodies ... in the body is natural but there is a need for external objects. The objects of direct impact make the parts of the body to be liked, and the sexual needs are formed accordingly. Sexual needs appear in the process of perfecting the body with the natural environment and social circumstances. "The body's need is not exercised by behavior, it is fleeting, momentary; while the body is trained by behavior, the conditioned need is reproduced, recalled, and increased the need. Any behavior that is beneficial to the body will be repeated, long remembered, preferred, habitual, perfect" (Quoc,2021e, p.2572). The sexual act that occurs during the body's maturation is one of the forms of need creation. If there is no sexual need, the sexual object is not perceived, then sexual orientation such as heterosexual, homosexual, bisexual, asexual does not appear. When the object of sexual need is scarce, the object of sexual gratification changes, and when the object of sex becomes common, the erosion of the sense of the object of sex, the diversification of forms sexual satisfaction occurs.

If hunger and thirst do not appear, food and water are not perceived. If fatigue and stress do not appear, sleeping and resting is a waste of life. Body imbalance manifests as variation, manifesting in disease or sex. When disease appears, the need for treatment is inevitable, and when sex appears, the need to solve it is common. Satisfying sexual needs can increase immunity, produce antibodies, prevent prostate cancer, lower blood pressure, increase the sense of smell, and reduce stress. Sexual needs are repeated both in intensity and time, the sexual object is constantly perceived. The perceived object is the object of need that people want. Self-aware of being unbalanced should aim at different objects. The object that resolves the imbalance becomes the object of sex. The subject of sex is not programmed according to a given pattern in humans and some other animals such as dolphins and chimpanzees. Humans, dolphins, chimpanzees perform sexual acts for the purpose of orgasm. Most other species are sexually active during the female's estrus to increase the likelihood of pregnancy, but humans, dolphins, and chimpanzees engage in sexual behavior even when the female is not in heat. In most species, adult males are sexually active, but depending on when the female is in heat. The object of human sexuality is discovered or created.

Behavior is the object of sex, the object of sex is all different acts. But behavior is the unity between body and human, so the object of sex is all bodies and people. All different acts become objects of sex. But the behavior that satisfies orgasm becomes the object of sex. Without the object of sex, the distinction between heterosexual, homosexual, bisexual and asexual becomes superfluous. When sexual needs appear, it makes sense to connect and exchange between bodies and direct people. If the need to eat and drink is not satisfied, death is inevitable; If the need for sleep and rest is not satisfied, fatigue, stress appear, and sexual needs and imbalance are not resolved, diseases appear. Diseases appear due to an imbalance in the life process. One of the diseases caused by the need for sex is mental illness. But mental illness is primary, and other illnesses are secondary. If eating and drinking are inevitable phenomena, then sleeping, resting, and sex are common phenomena. Sexual behavior is like eating a bowl of rice, drinking a glass of water, taking a nap, resting a bit or scratching an itchy spot, massaging the body but it is different in that it is increased arousal and arousal.

Without the imbalance of life, variation occurs, then sexual knowledge and will do not appear. If the knowledge, the will to sex does not arise, then sex does not become a need. Sexual behavior is the unification between the needs of the body and the needs of the person. But different bodies have different sex acts, different sexuality. However, sexuality is determined by genetic, hormonal and environmental factors. Genetic factors, hormones are of the body, but the environment and external objects selected are human. The sexual need is based on the unity of the body and the person, while the sexual orientation is chosen by the individual. When the body is sexually satisfied in different selected situations, objects and methods, real people have different genders: heterosexual, homosexual, bisexual, asexual.

The perceived sexual object makes the will to perform a sexual act stronger, the sexual need manifests itself in the act of knowledge and will about the object of sex. The act of having knowledge, of having a will is an individual act. Thus, individual behavior and sexual behavior are both similar but different at the same time. Humans are not aware of the sexual need in the body, then sexual behavior does not appear. Sexual acts without knowledge and will, then sexual acts are bodily acts. Sexual behavior is a physical act, when this sexual act is intended to relieve the imbalance of the body, to release sexual desire. Orgasm satisfaction is the purpose, and sexual behavior is the means. But physical behavior is unconscious, instinctive behavior, this sexual act is irresponsible. Sexual behavior is irresponsible, the behavior is orgasmic, and the responsibility lies with the body. The body is responsible for paying a heavy price for health, or sacrificing life or having to carry different kinds of diseases after performing sexual acts such as HIV/AIDS, bacteria, viruses, parasites, gonorrhea,

syphilis, chlamydia, hepatitis B. But if the sexual act is irresponsible then the sex act is not charged with rape, sexual abuse, incest, pedophilia, masturbation, homosexuality, adultery... therefore, sexual behavior is responsible.

Sexual behavior is responsible, it is a personal act, so the individual must be responsible before the standards, or be responsible for problems at risk due to promiscuous sex, family unhappiness, divorce, or other unhappiness as a result of sexual behavior, or being responsible for the social problems caused by sexual behavior. A sexual act is an individual act when the sexual act is creative. Creative sexual behavior is not only for the purpose of orgasm but for the satisfaction of the sexual act. Orgasm is the means, and sexual behavior is the purpose. Sexual acts are purposeful, sexual acts are voluntary and disinterested. It is the dedication, taking service as joy, without needing to return, giving the gift of wealth, money, nobility but because the body is healthy as a form of sport, exercise, yoga, gymnastics, beauty. The dedication is both a satisfaction, an affirmation of the practical value of life, and a discovery of the object. Whenever there is any satisfaction between people, that satisfaction is sharing, empathy, trust, forgiveness, tolerance. Mutual dissatisfaction between people causes discord, selfishness, jealousy, suspicion, envy.

Sexual behavior is responsible, created not only to satisfy different behaviors but also to fill in the gaps of time, it goes beyond standards, different interests to return to self, understanding your partner through enjoying life's orgasms. The creation of a sexual need in that a change of sexual behavior or a change of sexual object is essentially the same. This change depends on the conditions and circumstances in which the sexual need arises, that is, depending on the conditions of the different stages of the body's development. Any sexual act that has been performed is easily repeated when conditions permit. Changing sexual needs by training different needs to replace or change the method of performing sexual acts or by diversifying sexual objects. This change leads to homosexuality, bisexuality, asexuality, masturbation, rarity, incest, pedophilia, prostitution, adultery, sextoy, sex dolls or the appearance of pretense orgasm, narcissism, sex addiction.

If sexual need is a physical defect, then not having sex is human perfection or sexual need is bodily perfection then not having sex is a defect of human. Perfection and imperfection compensate for each other so that life is balanced. When sex appears, the norms that bind and prohibit sex appear. Commandments, precepts and laws that take heterosexual sex as a standard, heterosexuality becomes the norm. If heterosexual standards are taken as a measure of social value, homosexuality, bisexuality, and asexuality are out-of-species behavior. Even the fact that "Physiological weakness is individual but physiological weakness does not perform sexual function is inevitable. But not performing a sexual function and not doing lust are the same conduct. Noble is not to do lewdness and physiological weakness is the norm or criterion is not to do lewdness and physiological weakness is noble"(Quoc, 2021e, p.2573).

Defective genitalia, modest size covered by clothes, deceitful behavior covered by norm. The standard of virginity is upheld, so technical chastity, non-penetrating sex, and surgical intervention appear. Therefore, it is not possible to take heterosexuality as a social standard to condemn and criticize homosexuality, bisexuality and asexuality. Those who discriminate, discriminate against homosexuals, bisexuals and asexuals are not at fault, but the fault is due to standards. But it must be admitted that homosexuality, bisexuality, asexuality are not diseases, but disease is the norm of traditions, commandments, precepts, laws, and money. If there is no standard, the distinction between heterosexual, bisexual, homosexual and asexual is superfluous. Norm is nobility but the price of nobility is measured in money. Money is valued, so when gay, bisexual, asexual have a lot of money, homosexuality, bisexuality, asexuality becomes the value and need of society.

Distinguishing between heterosexuality and homosexuality, bisexuality, and asexuality becomes cheo plays and comedies that make life lively. The reality of life for all heterosexuals, homosexuals, bisexuals, asexuals to return to themselves, to live honestly. All are of equal value, so there is no discrimination regarding sexual favors. Those who still discriminate between heterosexuals, homosexuals, bisexuals and asexuals become psychopaths of life and become slaves to things that are not human. Everyone who is able to be true to themselves in terms of sexual orientation is equal and equally noble. The creation of sexual behavior is very significant in helping the partner to be satisfied, the body to return to equilibrium, the population growth to be harmonized, the connection between individuals is simple but more frankly, dedication, direct service between people is strengthened... However, the creativity of sexual acts is not fully realized, the problems of life appear, the phenomena of sexual abuse causes sexually transmitted diseases, or social problems are unavoidable.

The change between the means and the purpose of sexual behavior in the process of development

Labor produces wealth, property and sexual acts change objects, give birth to generations. Labor takes the means of production as the object, while the sexual act takes the human as the object. When the means of production are scarce, people become objects of living and vice versa. Possession of property and property by labor and possession of people by sexual acts share the same nature as privately - owned. The exchange between wealth and property with people is the exchange between labor and sexual acts. Labor is individual, sexual behavior is universal and vice versa. In exchange between the particular and the popular, the individual gets the price, the popular lowers the price. Sexual acts become popular, the population is larger, labor creates wealth, property becomes a need. Wealth, property becomes a universal need that allows private sexual behavior to

emerge. When the private ownership system was born, the standards of fidelity, forbidding lust, not wanting to marry people, adultery, filial piety, chastity, not murder, and monogamy appeared.

The private ownership was born, and standards emerged defining ownership rights among individuals in organizations. The norms state that “people possess each other in the family; implementation of commandments and precepts is that monks possess each other in religion; law enforcement are mutually owned officials in the state; exchanging, buying and selling money is mutual ownership between businessmen in the company. Loyalty is mutual ownership among people in an organization. Loyal to one organization is not loyal to another, if the organizations have different means and purposes. The development process from family, religion, state, to company is mutual inheritance in the issue of ownership behavior. Family of grandparents, parents, spouses, children. The religion of the monks. State of officials. The company of entrepreneurs” (Quoc, 2021e, p.2576).

The simple, direct exchange of sexual acts results in both direct orgasms, so it does not carry the meaning of hope and promise, loan and return. The sexual act is the act of creation, so it is one of the driving forces of life. Creativity that meets a universal need is socialized as a commodity for exchange. In a creative sexual act, sex is an exchange of a particular need with a universal need. At that time, satisfying sexual needs is no longer a simple and direct exchange, but an exchange with complex elements. Complicated factors intermingled in the exchange, purchase and sale of sexual acts. This exchange is masked by reciprocity, love, marriage, knowledge, standards, power, money, possessions. Sexual acts and living activities are common needs that are always created, so there is a mutual exchange. The relationship between bodies and people is no longer about satisfying sexual needs but also about exchanging and buying and selling materials for living. The sexual act that meets the common need, the sexual act will also earn money to live on. Any behavior that is exchanged, bought and sold to earn money is a commodity. But behavior is not separate from bodies and people, so the body and person are commodities.

Society needs money to exchange, buy and sell essential goods, and sex is a need, sex acts to earn a living. If sex acts are easier to earn more money than other forms of labor, then sexual acts become a social value, considered a livelihood. Sexual behavior contributes to creating jobs, distributing products, overcoming the gap between rich and poor, and eliminating discrimination. Liberate women by making men no longer enslaved to frivolous norms, especially sexual ones. If selling sex to women is vile, the people buying sex are no better. Husband and wife having sex and exchanging money, helping each other is no better than prostitution. The family is the most basic organization of life, but it turns out to be disguised as prostitution, or a standard of loyalty to mask impotence; And adultery and divorce are just the removal of falsehood in the husband and wife relationship. When sex is still an essential need of life, it is meaningless to prohibit the exchange and sale of sexual acts. But it is reasonable to ban sexual acts for people who are physiologically weak, helpless, apathetic, reluctant to have sex or who worship the norm. Making a living by standards and sexual behavior is the same. If making money by sex acts is a lowly job, then making money by standards is equally noble, but making money by sex acts is still more honest.

Sexual acts are a means of earning a living, sexual acts will be created like other goods to meet social needs. The creativity of sex consists in constantly renewing, or changing the way the sexual act is performed, or changing the object, or creating the object of sex. Sexual behavior is a commodity that distorts the relationship between bodies and people. This relationship to satisfy orgasm is not just pure sex, but in which there is an exchange and purchase that is covered by standards and money. The need for sex is essential and common in life, then binding standards and prohibiting sexual acts appear. But the norm of prohibiting and binding sexual behavior is always associated with the blessing, or punishment of work, occupation. It is an exchange between sexual needs and living needs; Satisfying one need at the expense of another. If sexual standards don't affect jobs and occupations, then those standards are meaningless.

Love, marriage, family, religion, state, company appear either for a livelihood, or for sexual gratification but are masked by various forms of exchange. Family, religion, state, company are different professional organizations, but sexual acts threaten the existence of organizations, the norms of sexuality are established by such organizations make, amend and supplement. Family traditions; commandments, precepts of religion; State law, corporate money is important for making a living but is also very easily distorted by sexual norms. The standards that bind, prohibit sex directly related to the occupation of organizations. If you violate the sexual standards of organizations, you will lose your reputation, resign, cut your job, or be forced to quit, which will directly affect your career and earning behavior. But free people violate sexual norms, the loss of jobs and livelihoods is indirect. Sexual behavior is distorted by different occupations. Homosexual, bisexual, and asexual phenomena appear accordingly.

Physiological weakness, impotence, frigidity not performing sexual functions are inevitable. This phenomenon is unique but meets the needs of life. In the context of a large population, scarce means of living, social benefits such as employment, health care, and education have not yet met the population; Sexually transmitted diseases and social problems caused by sexual relations, standards in the field of sex are necessary. When love, marriage, family, religion, state, company appear, sexual norms appear. The prohibition of rape, do not do lewdness, no prostitution make sexual acts scarce, so this standard is honored as noble, as a measure of social value.

Following the right standards is noble, failing to comply with the standards is lowly. But the norm is a common spiritual need, and performing the sexual act is common. Sexual demand is a common phenomenon, so it is possible to do business, buy and sell sexual acts like buying and selling other essential goods. Trading in sexual behavior is one form of redistribution of social values. Noble and lowly are expressed in the amount of wealth, more or less money. Producing and trading in goods to serve sexual needs becomes the sex economic sector.

As sexual behavior is still a need, the business and production of equipment to serve sexual needs is economic efficiency. The production of aphrodisiacs, aids, sextoys, sex dolls, prostitution, plastic surgery, engineering surgery of the genitals, plastic surgery, accessories, beauty tools will become popular. But these goods meet customers with special circumstances in terms of work, economic conditions, and different circumstances. But the production of these goods is popular, so it is not economically viable when the technology, level, high productivity, beautiful design, and low cost. If the goods produced are economically efficient, they must be special goods. Human, body, behavior is a special commodity, it has the ability to meet maximum needs by creating different behaviors, including sexual acts. This particular sex commodity is multifunctional, it can both change the need, change the way it is performed and the audience is rich and diverse. When sexual behavior is a product of creation, the individual becomes the exclusive commodity in satisfying sexual needs. When sex is fully exposed to human nature, human science has the conditions to develop, medicines to prolong life, cure diseases, improve capacity are produced to support relationships sex. The tools, drugs, and means of support to meet sexual needs are rich in design, lengthening, increasing intensity, variety of positions, creating stimulation, excitement but it cannot can replace human sexual behavior in terms of aesthetics, sensuality, passion, creativity, perception, discovery. All the properties of nature that need to be discovered, invented, and searched for are fully revealed in human sexual relations.

Personalization is an exclusive commodity that meets the sexual needs of a particular customer. When referring to the sex goods market, individual customers choose sex goods that meet their needs well. This choice manifests in the form of love, cohabitation, living before marriage, the rest is satisfying each other in terms of economic conditions. Family is a place where children have a need for the truth about the father, but when biotechnology and DNA testing become commonplace, family is meaningless. In relationships between people who are bound together into family, religious, state, corporate organizations by means of money or sexual norms. Sexual norms can replace money in exchange and connection between individuals with specific circumstances. Family, religious, state, and corporate organizations are ultimately linked between individuals either because they have a job to make a living, or to satisfy their sexual needs, or to maintain the race. Living and maintaining the race are different forms of satisfying needs, but it is not alien to sexual behavior. Money, power, sex can be exchanged, bought and sold in different standard forms.

Satisfying sexual behavior between heterosexuals in maintaining the race, but that relationship is distorted by the norm. When sexual behavior is distorted, it is compensated by other needs, such as the need for work, entertainment, standards, money, power, love, family, children... Direct sex between people is true, but that relationship is affected by the different needs of society, making sexual behavior distorted, sexual orientation distorted. The truth about orgasmic satisfaction is distorted, and falsehoods in the sexual field such as fake homosexuality, fake orgasm, divorce, adultery appear. The standards not to do lust, loyalty, love, care, help each other ... appear to cover physiological weakness, impotence, apathy in life. "As much as people lose the truth, the rest is compensated by such falsehoods, such a deviation in the direct and inevitable relationship between people. The particular necessity becomes the universal norm manifesting as the false nature of the spiritual life" (Quoc, 2021a, p.4213). Sex slavery, trafficking in children, women, and murder appear in the condition that sexual acts are commodities.

The purpose of orgasm is achieved, the birth of children, or direct relationships between heterosexuals lose all meaning. If there is no sexual act and orgasm is still achieved, childbirth no longer has a natural meaning but a social meaning. "In that natural species relationship, man's relationship with nature is directly man's relationship with man, and man's relationship with man is directly man's relationship with nature is, of course, the natural vocation of man himself. Thus, in that relationship expressed in the form of feelings, in the form of concrete facts, the situation is: for humans, human nature has become the natural world" (Marx& Engel, p.166). Sexual gratification is universal, procreation is particular. When wars, epidemics, natural disasters, scarce means of living cause the population to decrease and the demand for a large population appears, population reproduction becomes a social need. Maintaining the race, satisfying sex not only has natural meaning but also has social meaning. Sexual norms change, procreation is a social responsibility. If life does not exist, then sexual needs lose all meaning, and if social life does not exist, life has meaning only when sex is satisfied. Sex is no longer a need, the genitals only have the function of urination, medical facilities that operate on the genital organs can earn a lot of money. Repairing, suppressing to no longer have sexual desire is a common need, and drugs to reduce sexual desire will be produced.

The social responsibility of each individual is to maintain the species. Procreation is the performance of sexual acts. Performing sexual acts is socially responsible. Giving up sexual behavior is irresponsible. Sexual irresponsibility is to give up one's means of sustaining one's life and at the same time to destroy the reproductive

tract. Irresponsible does not take life as a pleasure, but takes each other's death as a goal. Taking death as the goal is not taking the maintenance of the species as a joy. Giving up the sexual need to become an annihilation of oneself will not allow others to live, that is a person who is not human. All children are born without fault but the fault of irresponsible parents. Maintaining the race is a personal responsibility, so having a baby is a consideration, considering health, education, and adulthood becomes a life purpose. Humans carry different means and purposes, which are natural and human, so maintaining the breed is a continuation of the means and goals in the development process. Maintaining the species is both a natural product and a product of society. Babies are born with "capable feelings of human enjoyment and self-assertion as intrinsic human forces"(Marx & Engel, p.167).

The maintenance of the race is a responsibility, so the responsibility becomes a need in the maintenance of the race. The maintenance of the species becomes the object of perception. Creative sexual acts appear homosexual, bisexual, asexual; Sexual aids, sterilization, contraceptives, family planning appeared to overcome the population explosion. However, the population explosion is directly related to sexual behavior. With a large population, population needs becoming secondary, reproductive restriction becoming a social responsibility, the phenomena of homosexuality, bisexuality and asexuality also become common. Procreation is particular, and labor is universal. Labor is common, hard-working, diversified by different professions, asexuality is common, and sexual needs are specific, human activities such as bees, hard-working ants, etc. hard at work, but do not forget the way, the way back. The tendency towards sexual development is always consistent with the population's need to be natural, it ensures ecological balance, but ensures the distribution of social values. Variations and deviations in sexual orientation are inevitable, historical specific but still ensure the general trend of human development.

The maintenance of the species is a necessity, the act of reproduction is a commodity. Trading in reproductive behavior will make a lot of money. Medical facilities related to obstetrics, plastic surgery, technology, sperm banks, hired pregnancy, family planning, safe abortion, artificial insemination, assisted reproductive technology; Treatment of diseases such as difficulty in sex, erectile dysfunction, impotence, frigidity, impotence, physiological weakness will appear more and more common. Drugs will continue to be produced for sexual needs such as Viagra, Cialis, Levitra, Dapoxetine. When sex is still a need, human science has conditions to appear, especially in the field of medicine in terms of cosmetic surgery, technical surgery on gender has conditions to develop. The business of sex acts is one of the important economic sectors, it contributes to the redistribution of social values, limiting the process of disparity between rich and poor, discrimination between people. The phenomena of heterosexuality, homosexuality, bisexuality, asexuality or diversification of ways of performing sexual acts do not solve social problems such as population explosion and food shortage. Create the necessary conditions for human science to have a common appearance.

Conclusion

The human body and the body are united with the need in behavior. Man is the need of the body and the body is the ability to satisfy the need. When man is the purpose, the body is the means and vice versa. The body satisfying man is a human act, when man satisfying the body is a bodily act. Sex is one of the essential needs of life, sexual behavior is both a human behavior and a physical act. The sexual act is both physically balanced and creative. The creation of sexual acts makes for the richness of objects and ways of performing sexual acts. Money and sex are common needs, sexual acts can earn a living. When sexual acts are goods, it is possible to produce and trade in tools and accessories to support sexual acts. Trading, trading in sexual acts is one of the forms of product distribution and socio-economic development.

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